

THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN STUDENTS PERFORMANCE IN RURAL AND URBAN AREAS: A CASE STUDY OF CHAMARAJANAGARA DISTRICT

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Abstract

Education is the most important aspect in any society development. Present day's school has to play a major role in ensuring the successful of the development of the society. As for students, they need to have good skills and has to be proactive with an appropriate futuristic set of mind. Further, students are also need to be active in co curriculum activity along with high academic achievement. The learning environments also have major roles to play in learning and the area where the students' lives can determine their performance in their studies. In this present research data has been collected through primary survey for the year 2021-2022, for this primary survey totally 500 students were interviewed through questionnaire. Which means there were from each taluk 50 students from rural and 50 students from urban area has involved in this survey from selected schools of the study region. Compare to rural and urban area in urban area student performance is more than the urban area. Still need to improve student performance in rural areas of the study region, because of many region many of the student perform not well compare to urban area, and also students are say in rural area while giving the answers and interacting to others than urban area.

Key word: Primary, Good, Average, Interact.

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Introduction:

In these present days education is the most important aspect in any society development. Present day's school has to play a major role in ensuring the successful of the development of the society. As for students, they need to have good skills and has to be proactive with an appropriate futuristic set of mind. Further, students are also need to be active in co curriculum activity along with high academic achievement. The learning environments also have major roles to play in learning and the area where the students' lives can determine their performance in their studies. There were many reasons for the variations in achievement such

as geographic location, resources, availability of technology and also the quality of teachers. These studies want to investigate the differences between students performance in rural and urban areas.

Aim of the Study

The main aim of the study is to investigate the differences between student's performances in rural and urban areas.

Study Area

Chamarajanagara District is the southern-most district in the state of Karnataka. Chamarajanagara town is the headquarters of this district; it is consisting of 5 taluks they are Chamarajanagara, Gundlupet, Kollegala, Hanur and Yalandur. It is bordered by Mysore and Mandya district of Karnataka state in the North, Nilgiris and Coimbatore districts of Tamil Nadu state in the South-East, Waynad district of Kerala state in South-West. The Geographical area is 5101 Sq. Kms. Study area is lying between 76°24' and 77°43' east longitudes and 11°32' and 12°16' north latitudes. The Chamarajanagara district has well drainage system, the main water sources are- Suvarnavathi, Pallar, Moyar and UdutoreHalla. The soils of the district can be broadly classified as the red-loam, sandy loam and black cotton soil. In the taluk of Chamarajanagar, Gundlupet and Kollegala which is deep red loam base occasionally interspersed with black soils. The red sandy loamy soils are derived from the granites and gneisses. The south-western and southern parts of the district are begins in the edge of western Ghats, well endowed with sufficient rainfall and known for the production of variety of reunified crops. In addition to reunified cultivation, the canal network of Suvarnavathi and Chikkahole. Location of study area has shown in Map 1.

Map.No.1:Geographical Location Map of Chamarajanagara District

Data Base and Methodology:

In this present research data has been collected through primary survey for the year 2021-2022, for this primary survey totally 500 students were interviewed through questionnaire. Which means there were from each taluk 50 students from rural and 50 students from urban area has involved in this survey from selected schools of the study region. All these have tabularised by using statistical application's for Rural and Urban area of the study area.

Results and Discussion

This present study mainly focused on performance of students in rural and urban area in each taunks of the Chamarajanagara district. to examine the student performance different questionnaire has used in both rural and urban area of the study region. They are as follows below:

- Test questions on basic maths and general science
- Quizzes on basic mental ability sums, general knowledge
- Pick and speech on their last year academic concepts
- Writing test based on showing of charts and models relate to mathematics and social science concepts

After interacting and collecting the information the students performance level has been classified into two categories, they are; 1) Good 2) Average. (Refer Table No1)

Table No 1 Chamarajanagara District: Students Performance Level in School in Ruraland Urban Area

Figures are in Percent

Sl No	Name of the Taluk	Rural		Urban	
		Good	Average	Good	Average
1	Chamarajanagar	28	19	30	20
2	Gundlupet	14	28	21	30
3	Kollegal	7	8	20	19
4	Hanur	45	34	19	21
5	Yalandur	6	11	10	10
6	Total	100	100	100	100

Source: Compiled by Author

According to study in rural area student performance and learning level has been analysed and classified into two classification such as Good and Average. According to study in Chamarajanagara taluk there is 28 percent of students are in good level of learning, in Gundlupet taluk there is 14 percent of students in good level of learning, in Kollegal taluk there is 7 percent of students are in good level of learning, in Hanur taluk there is 45 percent

of students are in good level of learning and in Yalandur taluk there is 6 percent of students are in good level of learning. Whereas in average category there is 19 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Chamarajanagara taluk, there is 28 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Gundlupet taluk, there is 8 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Kollegal taluk, there is 34 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Hanur taluk and there is 11 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Yalandur taluk of the study region. (Refer Map No 2)

Map No 2 Chamarajanagara District: Students Performance Level in School in Rural Area

Whereas in urban area in Chamarajanagara taluk there is 30 percent of students are in good level of learning, in Gundlupet taluk there is 21 percent of students in good level of learning, in Kollegal taluk there is 20 percent of students are in good level of learning, in Hanur taluk there is 19 percent of students are in good level of learning and in Yalandur taluk there is 10 percent of students are in good level of learning. Whereas in average category there is 20 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Chamarajanagara taluk, there is 30 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Gundlupet taluk, there is 19 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Kollegal taluk, there is 21 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Hanur taluk and there is 10 percent of students belong to average level of learning in Yalandur taluk of the study region. (Refer Mao No 3)

Map No 3 Chamarajanagara District: Students Performance Level in School in Urban Area

Conclusion

Measuring the student performance or learning level has usually takes the form of summative assessments such as standardized tests, exams, quick speak interaction. This also monitors performance data on a micro-scale by using aligned formative assessments, such as performance tasks or weekly quizzes, to monitor student skill. Compare to rural and urban area in urban area student performance is more than the urban area. Still need to improve student performance in rural areas of the study region, because of many region many of the student perform not well compare to urban area, and also students are say in rural area while giving the answers and interacting to others than urban area.

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